

FORMATION OF LEXICAL COMPETENCE IN TEACHING ENGLISH AS A SECOND FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Anotation: *The modern linguistic situation, characterized by the growth of multilingualism, has awakened an increased research interest in the phenomenon of linguistic interference that occurs in the study of foreign languages. To date, there are a large number of studies devoted to the influence of the native language on the study of a foreign language, but the problem of the interaction of two studied foreign languages with each other is not covered enough. The article is devoted to the formation of lexical competence in teaching English for professional purposes to international students who previously studied French, taking into account interlingual interference. Long-term pedagogical practice allowed us to assume that in the study of diplomatic terminology, lexical interference will arise and play a significant role, the source of which is the French language. The author puts forward a hypothesis that the process of forming lexical skills will be more effective if a teaching methodology is built taking into account the transfer of skills and abilities from FL1, with the inclusion in the educational process of a set of exercises for mastering vocabulary based on an authentic text. The author comes to the conclusion about the expediency of developing a special educational and methodological complex for teaching a second foreign language and offers his own version, which combines the use of an integrative set of exercises for teaching vocabulary in the process of intensive reading with the methodology of critical pedagogy. The author presents the results of a pilot study confirming the effectiveness of the proposed methodology in terms of forming lexical skills, expanding vocabulary and reducing the number of errors associated with language interference.*

Keywords: *English language, French language, critical pedagogy, specialty language, international relations, lexical interference, second foreign language, teaching methods.*

ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ЛЕКСИЧЕСКОЙ КОМПЕТЕНЦИИ ПРИ ОБУЧЕНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ КАК ВТОРОМУ ИНОСТРАННОМУ

Аннотация: *Современная языковая ситуация, характеризующаяся ростом многоязычия, пробудила повышенный исследовательский интерес к феномену языковой интерференции, возникающему при изучении иностранных языков. На сегодняшний день существует большое количество исследований, посвященных влиянию родного языка на изучение иностранного, но проблема взаимодействия двух изучаемых иностранных языков друг с другом освещена недостаточно. Статья посвящена вопросам формирования лексической компетенции при обучении английскому языку для профессиональных целей иностранных студентов, ранее изучавших французский язык, с учетом межъязыковой интерференции. Многолетняя педагогическая практика позволила предположить, что при изучении дипломатической терминологии будет возникать и играть существенную роль лексическая интерференция, источником которой является французский язык. Автор выдвигает гипотезу о том, что процесс формирования лексических навыков будет более эффективным, если методика обучения будет построена с учетом передачи навыков и умений из ИЯ1, с включением в учебный процесс комплекса упражнений на овладение лексикой на основе аутентичного текста. Автор приходит к выводу о целесообразности разработки специального учебно-методического комплекса для обучения второму иностранному языку и предлагает свой вариант, сочетающий использование*

интегративного комплекса упражнений для обучения лексике в процессе интенсивного чтения с методология критической педагогики. Автор представляет результаты пилотного исследования, подтверждающие эффективность предложенной методики в плане формирования лексических навыков, расширения словарного запаса и снижения количества ошибок, связанных с языковой интерференцией.

Ключевые слова: *английский язык, французский язык, критическая педагогика, язык специальности, международные отношения, лексическая интерференция, второй иностранный язык, методика обучения.*

INTRODUCTION

In this regard, it seems important to study the specifics of multilingual education, to identify the difficulties that arise when teaching a second language, and to outline ways to overcome them. At present, this issue attracts close attention of researchers, which is due to the modern linguistic situation, characterized by an increase in polylingualism. Thus, the phenomenon of linguistic interference - deviations from linguistic norms, which arise in the speech of multilinguals as a result of the fact that they speak foreign languages, that is, as a result of linguistic contact. The task of applying the theory of language interference in pedagogical practice arises, which we are trying to solve in this work. Basic approaches to the formation of lexical competence in the study of a foreign language in the field of professional communication Mastering professional terminology is the primary task of learning a foreign language in the field of professional communication. Lexical competence in the field of professional communication implies knowledge of general and professional terminology, as well as the ability to use the acquired vocabulary in speech activity. The criteria for successful work with vocabulary, according to the main provisions of the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages. There are the number of words and set expressions that need to be mastered, the possession of sufficient vocabulary for the implementation of speech activity, the regularity of using the learned material and control over this process; knowledge of the differences between active and passive vocabulary, knowledge control. These requirements are easily extrapolated to the field of professional vocabulary. During intensive work with the text, students study in detail a small passage or a short text of 150-200 words, while the tasks that the text is equipped with consist of a large number of lexical exercises and text comprehension tasks, the total volume of which significantly exceeds the volume of the text itself.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The goals of intensive work on the text are a detailed understanding of the text and the study of linguistic phenomena using the text as an example, the development of linguistic thinking, the expansion of vocabulary students and their language level (taking into account the subject, logical and linguistic complexity), compliance with a certain topic, cognitive value of the text, semantic completeness and structuredness of the text, representation in the corpus of educational texts of various types (descriptive, narrative, argumentative, informational, explanatory). Authenticity of textual material of various genres of scientific, journalistic and pragmatic styles. In our case of teaching professional vocabulary of a second foreign language, such a criterion as the intercultural nature of the information presented in the text.

Application of critical pedagogy methodology Intensive reading of complicated authentic texts in the specialty as a pedagogical technique designed to optimize the teaching of terminology in terms of language contact, organically fits into the methodological concept of critical pedagogy, the advantages of which we considered earlier. The specifics of the methods of critical pedagogy

is the rejection of the rationally dogmatic methods of traditional teaching in favor of an approach that takes into account the diversity of positions and points of view of the participants in the educational process, their individual characteristics. This approach contributes to the development of professional competence of trainees to the greatest extent. Within the framework of critical pedagogy, the deconstruction of traditional roles is carried out, implying the activity of a teacher as a carrier of knowledge and the passivity of a student as a recipient, the delegation of part of the teaching powers to students is practiced. Methods of critical pedagogy contribute to the development of students' reading skills and understanding of professionally oriented foreign texts, help to cover the whole variety of forms of modern scientific texts, both on paper and on electronic media. In particular, the results of a pilot study conducted by the author demonstrated the expediency of using critical pedagogy methods in teaching reading and understanding of professionally oriented texts in English. The opportunity for a teacher to teach (in the language being studied) the discipline of specialization gives additional interest to the classes. Methods of Teaching the Vocabulary of English as a Second Foreign Language World practice has accumulated a baggage of methods of teaching the vocabulary of English as a foreign language. Since the native language of the students is Russian, for the purposes of our study, the methodology developed within the framework of the national school of teaching a foreign language, which is based on the use of an integrative set of exercises for teaching vocabulary in the process of reading, turned out to be the most relevant includes the following pre - text stage : actualization and associative presentation of lexical units relevant for the understanding of the text ; stage of reading the text: perception of new vocabulary in the text, its semantization (formation of a receptive lexical skill); text (formation of reproductive information processing of a productive lexical skill, production of a creative statement - free creative inclusion of vocabulary in speech situations based on a complete understanding of the form, meaning and functional features. Taking the above methodology of teaching vocabulary as a basis, we adapted it to the tasks of teaching English as a second foreign language with first French in the field of professional communication. We took into account the expediency of applying the method of intensive reading based on authentic complicated texts, as well as the methods of critical pedagogy, noted above. a set of exercises for teaching professional vocabulary has been developed , which includes exercises that promote recognition , perception and understanding of various units of professional vocabulary. This set of exercises is included in the system of exercises aimed at teaching intensive reading as a type of speech activity using the methods of critical pedagogy. Within the framework of this integrative set of exercises, vocabulary is taught in three stages. At the first (pre - text) stage of work with vocabulary , exercises aimed at forming paradigmatic and syntagmatic connections are used to ensure the primary consolidation of lexical competence in the field of professional communication.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The second stage of the formation of the lexical skill is combined with the text stage and the development of intensive reading skills with the help of critical pedagogy techniques. At this stage, a variety of oral and written exercises are used, which develop the ability to use terms, choose a term from a number of presented ones according to the situation, and the ability to fully and accurately understand the text. The third stage of work on the text and professional vocabulary, corresponding to the post-text stage, implies the consolidation of lexical knowledge and skills, as well as their activation in the process of using them in various forms of written and oral communication (speech exercises). In addition, you can apply tasks for working out thematic terminology in order to eliminate potential lexical interference, which may include the selection

of synonyms / antonyms, filling in gaps, two-way translation of lexical units in different contexts, exercises on word compatibility, the formation of single-root words with the help of appropriate affixes. The process of forming lexical skills in teaching English as a second foreign language (FL2) will be more effective if you build a methodology for teaching professional vocabulary, taking into account the transfer from the first foreign language (FL1) of speech, language and general educational skills and abilities, using methodological techniques critical pedagogy, with the inclusion in the educational process of an integrated set of exercises for the assimilation of vocabulary based on an authentic text in the specialty taking into account the abilities of students, with the presentation and development of professional vocabulary in the process of intensive reading. Purpose of the study To test the effectiveness of the methodology for teaching professional vocabulary of the English language as a FL2, taking into account the language experience of students, based on a set of lexical exercises integrated into the system of exercises for teaching reading, taking into account interlingual transfer, using the methodology of critical pedagogy.

CONCLUSIONS

The results of the study confirm the hypothesis of the presence and high significance of language interference in the study of professional English as a second foreign language with the first French, the source of the interference is French. Typical mistakes of students depend on their language experience and they are due to the language interference of FL1 and FL2. The main source of errors is fully or partially assimilated cognate words. The expediency of developing a special educational and methodological complex for teaching a second foreign language, which combines the use of an integrative set of exercises for teaching vocabulary in the process of intensive reading with the methodology of critical pedagogy. In the course of experiential learning the expediency and effectiveness of the proposed methodology was confirmed in terms of the formation of lexical skills, intensive reading skills, expanding vocabulary and reducing the number of errors associated with language interference. The results obtained show that the use of an integrative set of exercises for teaching vocabulary in the process of intensive reading using the methodology of critical pedagogy contributes to the formation of lexical skills. Qualitative and quantitative research data indicate that the use of the developed methodology in parallel with the methods of critical pedagogy has a positive effect on the assimilation of lexical material, develops intensive reading skills and expands the vocabulary of students, reducing lexical language interference and reducing typical errors. The results obtained can be used in the process of further research into the phenomenon of lexical interference, for the development of methods for the formation of lexical skills in the study of a second foreign language, in the course of practical classes in teaching professional English, as well as in the development of special textbooks and teaching materials for teaching a second foreign language.

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